

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

УДК:378.011.3-051.:784+615(043)

FORMATION OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCES ON THE BASIS OF HEALTH-SAVING TECHNOLOGIES OF FUTURE MUSIC TEACHERS

Vrubel H.

concertmaster of the Department of Theory and Methodology of Music Education and Choreography, Melitopol State Pedagogical University named after Bohdan Khmelnytskyi (Melitopol) 59 Scientific town St., Zaporozhye, Zaporizhzhia region, 69000, Ukraine, <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5890-2718X>

Mitieva A.

concertmaster of the Department of Theory and Methodology of Music Education and Choreography, Melitopol State Pedagogical University named after Bohdan Khmelnytskyi (Melitopol), 59 Scientific town St., Zaporozhye, Zaporizhzhia region, 69000, Ukraine, <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6304-915X> <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14169123>

Abstract

The article examines the issue of the relationship between professional training and the requirements of the modern educational paradigm for professional education. In the article, the author reveals the specifics of the implementation of health-saving technologies in the process of training future music teachers of professional competence. The essence of the phenomenon of the professional competence of future music teachers is substantiated and substantiated.

The essence of the concepts "competence", "professional competence", "artistic competence", "cultural competence", "health-preserving competence", "health-preserving technologies", "polycompetence" was determined, and the specifics of their application in the process of training future specialists were revealed. The implementation of health-preserving technologies in the process of training future teachers of musical art is substantiated on the basis of competence-through and humanistic approaches. The article highlights the issue of structuring the professional competence of future music teachers without primary music education.

The interpretation of scientists regarding the essence of the professional competence of future specialists and its structure is presented. It was determined that the professional competence of future teachers of musical art covers the knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for teaching musical art and developing the musical culture of students. The author's definition of the professional competence of future music teachers is provided. Emphasis is placed on the lack of consensus among scientists regarding the name of competence. It was found that the professional competence of future music teachers has a wide range of components and involves the presence of both theoretical knowledge and practical skills. It is key to successful teaching of music and formation of musical culture in students. It has been established that the formation of professional competence is directly influenced by the individual psychological characteristics of the student of education.

Research has been conducted and the main trends in determining the components of the professional competence of future music teachers have been clarified. On the basis of a comparative analysis, the author's structure of the professional competence of future teachers of musical art is proposed, which are motivational-value, cognitive-active, creative, personal components and provides for the identification of the individuality of the future specialist, its cultivation, as one of the means of his professional formation. It was established that the structure of the professional competence of the future music teacher has its own specificity, which is determined by the purpose and content of pedagogical activity in the school, covers the entire range of professional activity, which includes its musical-pedagogical, psychological-pedagogical and methodical components, and reflects a number of musical-performing and musical-theoretical abilities and skills.

Keywords: competence, professional competence, artistic competence, cultural competence, health-preserving competence, health-preserving technologies, polycompetence.

Problem statement: In the context of the modernization of higher education, there is an urgent need to train a specialist of a high professional level, capable of self-realization, capable of creative construction of his/her life, focused on personal choice and personal responsibility. Today, this problem is becoming increasingly important in the training of music teachers, who must develop professional competence during their years of study at a higher education institution. It is well known that university graduates are not always competitive in the labor

market, so the actual theoretical and practical problem of professional pedagogy is to change the strategies of training specialists. The solution to this problem will ensure the improvement of the quality of higher education of specialists and on this basis the competitiveness of graduates and the prestige of Ukrainian higher education will increase significantly in the world educational space.

Analysis of recent research and publications:

The problem of reorientation and improvement of the professional education system is discussed in

pedagogical science quite actively. The analysis of scientific and pedagogical literature shows the existence of different approaches to the definition of the concept of "competence", shows the great interest of domestic and foreign researchers in this problem on the one hand, and on the other hand, indicates that this problem is not solved both in theory and practice. Scientific works of such researchers as: V. Anishchenko, I. Bekh, I. Zyazyun, I. Zymnia, L. Mosol, O. Ovcharuk, A. Khutorsky, T. Shamova focus on the theoretical and methodological foundations of the problem. The works of V. Bolotov, S. Kozak, T. Sorochan, V. Vvedensky are devoted to the issue of modeling and the problem of forming the competencies of future specialists. In the field of music education, various aspects of professional competencies are revealed: from a complex multidimensional phenomenon (I. Mykhailychenko, P. Tretyakov) to the definition of key competencies (I. Zymnia, T. Shamova) and certain aspects of the formation of professional competencies of future music teachers (O. Horbenko, N. Murovana). Powerful scientists of our time, such as: O. Rudnytska, T. Padalka, O. Oleksiuk in their works reveal general issues of teaching methods in universities and the formation of various competencies of future music teachers.

However, the issue of optimizing the effective management of the educational process, its features and specifics in educational and artistic institutions in the light of the competence approach is not sufficiently covered. This problem still remains the subject of further heated discussions and research, and scientific, theoretical and practical searches continue. The purpose of the article: Taking into account the multifunctional orientation of the training of future music teachers, the purpose of the article is to highlight the issue of reorientation of their training to the output, activation of the educational process, taking into account the unity of professional training (conducting, choral, vocal) through the use of health-saving and modern teaching technologies aimed at the ability of university graduates to use professional knowledge in practice, as well as to outline ways to form the professional competence of future musical arts teachers.

Summary of the main research material: Modern music education needs a qualitative rethinking, which will be aimed at the organizational dynamic of the educational process, the use of effective pedagogical and the latest health-saving technologies, which will contribute to the quality training of future teachers of music, help higher education students to master professional competencies as the initial level of their professional training in performing and teaching activities.

The analysis of modern educational activities states the extensive nature of education in universities, which is characterized by an overload of curricula and disciplines, a focus on memorization and reproduction of educational information rather than on creative assimilation and use in practice, and the lack of independent search, which is significantly different from foreign education. According to contemporary

researcher G. Padalka, the existing system of teaching disciplines is characterized by a certain abstraction, detachment from the existing problems of the future profession in practice. Teachers often focus on abstract artistic and musical skills. In the author's opinion, professional training that ignores the needs of cultural and musical practice and is guided exclusively by the artistic direction does not ensure that the professional knowledge, skills and abilities acquired by higher education students in the process of studying are transformed into practical professional work.

In view of this, solving the problems of modern music education requires actualization and intensification of the professional orientation of training of music specialists, which involves achieving the unity of artistic and professional and general professional training of higher education applicants, determining the "organic interpenetration of the alloy of integration" of the tasks of future professional activity with the formation of knowledge, skills and abilities in the field of music and choral art. [4,p.250]

The need to substantiate a new paradigm of pedagogical education, which is directly related to professional musical competence, determines the optimal adaptation of future music teachers to the conditions of professional activity. There is no unanimous approach to understanding the definitions of the competency-based approach in scientific and pedagogical science. Modern scholars in their research highlight different interpretations of these concepts, their essence and content. We share the scientific opinion of S. Svitailo, who believes that the competence-based concept of vocational education is aimed at improving the training of specialists by forming their professional musical competence as a component of professionalism and covers personal characteristics, theoretical musical knowledge, and practical abilities in the field of professional musical activity. [8,p.670-675]

The professional musical competence of a future music teacher has its own peculiarities, which are due to the multifunctional nature of the profession. All of its components are organically interconnected: personal development, professional musical training, formation of general and musical culture, and the ability to carry out professional activities independently. In addition to outstanding musical talent and professionalism as a performer, every student of higher education must be a teacher, psychologist, organizer, and have the knowledge and skills of a music director and even an actor. Experts from the European Union define the concept of "competence" as "the ability to apply knowledge and skills," which means the active use of learning achievements in new situations in the educational process. The International Department of Standards for Learning, Achievement and Education defines the concept of competence as the ability to perform an activity, task or job competently. The concept of competence includes a set of knowledge, skills and attitudes that allow a person to act effectively or perform certain functions aimed at achieving certain

standards in a professional field or a certain activity [3, p.8-9].

H. Bibik, a modern powerful Ukrainian scientist, emphasizes that competencies "are acquired by a young person not only when studying a subject or a group of subjects, but also through non-formal education, as a result of environmental influences, etc. According to the scientist, the concept of "competence" is primarily a social norm alienated from the subject, a predetermined social norm for the educational training of a student, which is directly necessary for his or her high-quality productive activity in a particular educational field, that is, to some extent, it is a socially fixed result. The scientist believes that the result of the acquisition of competencies is competence, since the sign of competence is its general subject or specific nature, and competence implies a personal characteristic and attitude to the subject of activity. [1, p.409]

Thus, the concept of "competence" in the modern scientific literature is revealed by the following definitions that characterize this phenomenon:

- Knowledge, experience in any field;
- Basic characteristics of a person;
- Some internal, potential psychological qualities of a personality, which are further manifested in activity;
- An integrative characteristic of the quality of a graduate's training;
- A set of skills, knowledge in action;
- Ability, willingness, capacity;
- Quality of personality;
- Specific ability necessary for the effective performance of a specific action in a particular field, which includes highly specialized knowledge, specific subject skills, ways of thinking, understanding of responsibility for one's own actions.

The professional musical competence of a future music teacher has its own peculiarities, which are due to the specific nature of the profession - multifunctionality. It consists of many components that are organically interconnected. Analyzing the results of scientific research on the competence concept of education, the specifics and features of the educational process in music education universities (O. Rudnytska, H. Padalko, O. Oleksiuk, H. Kondratenko, N. Mosianko), we consider the professional competence of a future music teacher as a complex, integral, dynamic in its structure education that can be modified in accordance with the content and level of education.

A special form of reflection of reality is art, an aesthetic artistic phenomenon that conveys the beauty of the world around us, the inner world of a person through the comprehension of the fundamental categories of "beauty", "harmony", "perfection". The process of forming a competent personality includes an art criticism component, which implies awareness of various types of art, developed skills of perception of works of art, and the formation of artistic and creative skills.

Artistic competence is the ability to apply knowledge of the theory and history of art, world

culture, history of music and other arts in educational activities, the ability to analyze, evaluate and interpret - a concept that specifies general cultural competence. Let's try to define the main criteria of artistic competence by analyzing psychological, pedagogical, artistic, and musicological and pedagogical primary sources. In scientific works in the field of art education (G. Padalka, L. Mosol, O. Rudnytska, O. Shcholokova and others) it is indicated that the development of such qualities as: artistic taste, ideals, aesthetic knowledge and artistic and creative abilities, the ability to make judgments and the ability to self-improvement, is an indicator of the artistic development of the individual, which formed in the unity of emotional and sensual, cognitive (intellectual) and creative and activity components that can serve as general criteria for of artistic competence.

In modern pedagogical science, a separate area of methodological research, which is based on the complex influence of different types of art on the student's personality. The cultural competence in the theoretical and methodological context is highlighted in the works of contemporary Ukrainian researchers (O. Gurenko, S. Cherepanova), and theoretically generalized in the philosophical and pedagogical works of foreign scholars (B. Beam-Bud, B. Kononenko, A. Flier).

The cultural competence of a music teacher is a set of knowledge about culture in the broad and narrow sense of the word, which create a holistic picture of the world and indicate the role of the role of the discipline that clarifies this picture, allows you to determine the place of a person in this world and ways to change the world with the help of the knowledge gained.

Regarding music teachers, their cultural competence is defined as meaningful knowledge about culture, its clear structure, which provides the ability to make decisions in situations of solving cultural problems.

Cultural competence should be understood as a personality trait that allows one to feel oneself an object of the cultural and historical process, to be widely educated, to have knowledge in various fields of science and art, to understand the patterns of cultural development as a process of preserving and transmitting universal values, to be part of the modern world.

The analysis of scientific and methodological research in the field of pedagogy makes it possible to formulate a definition of the concept of cultural competence. Cultural competence is an integrated quality, which is expressed through the ability of a person to be spiritually and aesthetically educated, comprehensively knowledgeable, possess national and cultural knowledge (to understand the traditions, realities, customs, spiritual values of his/her people); to find the components of spiritual and material culture recorded in music and fine arts; to be able not only to use them appropriately but also to pass them on to students; to realize oneself and each person as a carrier

of a particular ethnic culture; to be able to see the common and different in the worldview of their carriers. Cultural competence is the basis for high-quality professional activity, the formation of national consciousness of the individual - a person who knows the language and culture of his or her nation, has a wealth of expressive means, and thinks creatively in different life situations.

Today's realities are such that the lesson, as the main form of organizing the educational process, is not considered modern if it does not take into account the health of the child, if health is damaged during lessons. Therefore, today it is important to create conditions for preserving the health of students, introducing health-saving technologies into the educational process. In this regard, the music lesson is unique, because music affects a person on three levels: vibrational, emotional and spiritual. Understanding and perceiving music is about feeling it with your ligaments, muscles, movements, and breath. The combination of art therapy in the form of various exercises, along with vocal therapy, rhythm therapy, fairy tale therapy, and color therapy, can be an effective method of health promotion for students, treatment of school neuroses that arise in the process of education, and in modern life in general.

Music has a healing function, affecting human biochemical processes. Scientists have proved that music can strengthen the immune system, improve metabolism and, as a result, help restore processes in the body.

An analysis of a large number of scientific sources has allowed us to identify some of the most meaningful definitions of the term "health competence". Thus, in the current State Standard of Basic and Complete General Secondary Education, the definition of "health-saving competence" is presented as "the ability of a student to apply a set of health-saving competences in a specific situation, to take care of their own health and the health of other people". I. Anokhina considers health-saving competence as a readiness to independently solve problems related to maintaining, strengthening and preserving health, both one's own and others'. T. Boichenko defines health-saving competence as a key competence and suggests the following features:

- Multifunctionality: this competence allows solving the problems of health care of a person, group of people, community and society in the space of all four components of health - physical, social, mental and spiritual;

- Super-subjectivity and interdisciplinarity: information about the formation, preservation, strengthening, use (or consumption), restoration and transfer of health takes place in all parts of continuous valeological education (preschool, school, undergraduate, postgraduate, adult education);

- Multidimensionality: due to the essence of human health as a multidimensional and holistic phenomenon. Ensuring a wide scope of personal development: studying ways and means of forming, preserving, strengthening, restoring and transferring

health, especially its spiritual component, has a personal focus.

O. Vashchenko considers health-saving competence as a process consisting of three stages, which differ from each other both in specific tasks and in the peculiarities of the methodology. The first stage is an initial familiarization with basic concepts and ideas, aimed at forming students' elementary knowledge of the components of a healthy lifestyle: an understanding of the basic rules of health; compliance with health standards, motivation to lead a healthy lifestyle. The second stage - in-depth study - focuses on a full understanding of the basics of a healthy lifestyle and points to the solution of the following tasks: clarifying ideas about the basics of health; achieving conscious implementation of the elementary rules for maintaining and improving health; formation of practical knowledge, skills, and abilities necessary in everyday life. The third stage - consolidation of knowledge, skills and abilities to maintain and improve health and their further improvement - involves the formation of the ability to maintain health and turn it into a habit that will be used in everyday life.

Thus, the use of health-saving technologies in the world is a way of organizing consistent actions in the course of educational and upbringing process, implementation of educational programs taking into account the peculiarities of individual health of students, peculiarities of their age, psychophysical, spiritual and moral state and development, preservation and strengthening of health, as a result of which a certain competence is formed.

The constant use of innovative and information and communication technologies is a component of the modern lesson of musical art and artistic culture. This encourages students to do independent research work, makes learning more diverse and vivid. Collective cognitive activity is quite emotional and teaches initiative. Children are engaged in creativity, form universal knowledge, independently formulate a problem, select sources and literature, interpret and evaluate events.

Conclusions:

The modern educational process is aimed at realizing the main goal - the formation of a competitive, competent personality, so the renewal of education is characterized by the search for non-traditional approaches to solving educational, developmental and educational tasks.

Having analyzed various scientific and pedagogical views, we can identify the specifics of competencies that are formed through the arts. Firstly, when a person communicates with artistic values, practical experience, the level of artistic knowledge, value-based artistic orientations are transformed into artistic and aesthetic competencies - health, art history, cultural studies - organic components of life competencies. Secondly, artistic and aesthetic competencies are built on a complex of interactions of interests, motives, attitudes, knowledge, skills that reflect the integrated results of learning in the field of art and the formed personal qualities. That is, the competencies that are formed in the process of art

education are of a personal, active and integrative nature.

Polycompetence as a readiness for artistic and creative self-realization, self-improvement and self-education in the field of art provides meta-subject knowledge and skills, among which self-regulation skills play a significant role.

References:

1. Encyclopedia of education/ Acad. ped. Sciences of Ukraine; [chief ed. V.G. Kremin].-K.: Yurinkom Inter, 2008.-1040p. p. 409.
2. Yerzhemskyi G.L. Psychology of conducting: Some issues of performance and creative interaction of the conductor with the musical team. - K.: Music, 1988. - 80p.
3. Ovcharuk O.V. Development of the competency-based approach: strategic orientations of the international community/O.V. Ovcharuk// competency-based approach in modern education: world experience and Ukrainian perspectives: Educational Policy Library/ [Under general ed. O.V. Ovcharuk].-K.: "k.i.s." 2004.-p.6-93.p.8-9
4. Padalka T.M. Art pedagogy (Theory and methods of teaching art disciplines): teaching. manual.- Kyiv: Education of Ukraine, 2008.-272p.) p.250)
5. Pedagogical mastery: Textbook / I.A. Zyazyun, L.V. Kramushenko, I.F. Krivonos and others; Under the editorship I.A. Zyazyuna. – 2nd ed., supplement. and processing - K.: Vyshcha shk., 2004.-422p.
6. Rudnytskaya O.P. Pedagogy: general and artistic: Education. manual. - K.: IZMN, 2002. - 270p.
7. Rudnytskaya O.P. Formation of musical perception in the system of development of pedagogical culture of the future teacher: Diss. dr. ped. of science / O.P. Rudnytskaya – K., 1994. – 431p.
8. Svitailo S. Competence training of a music teacher//Professional artistic education and artistic culture: challenges of the 21st century/Coll. the mother International scientific and practical conference - Kyiv, October 16-17, 2014 - pp. 670-675.